

The Tomb of Meresankh III

By Rania Eshaq, The Egyptian Museum in Cairo (EMC)

Entry tags: Religious Place, Egyptian Religions, Religious Group, Tomb, Archaeological monument

The mastaba-tomb of Meresankh III (G7530/7540) in the Eastern Cemetery at Giza was excavated by George Andrew Reisner of the Harvard University Museum of Fine Arts, Boston Expedition in 1927 and was subsequently published by Dows Dunham and William Kelly Simpson in 1974. The mastaba consists of two sections, an upper mastaba (G7530/7540) and a lower rock-cut tomb (G7530sub). The mastaba and rock-cut tomb are generally dated to the Fourth Dynasty of the Old Kingdom.

Date Range: 2620 BCE - 2570 BCE

Region: Giza

Region tags: Middle East, Africa, Egypt

The Giza Plateau, The tomb of Meresankh III

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace) ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Type of elevation

–Other [specify]: Giza Plateau

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general

populace)

↳ A single structure

— Yes

Notes: Burial place

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The structure has a definite shape

— Rectangular

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ One single feature

— Other [specify]: A tomb

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A group of structures:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

— Yes

Notes: Mastaba above the ground, tomb below the ground

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A group of features:

— Yes

Notes: Mastaba above the ground and a tomb under the ground

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

— Yes

Notes: Giza plateau/ The Giza pyramids area

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

— Other [specify]: A tomb/ Burial place

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: Reisner reconstructed the development of the Eastern Cemetery. Isolated structure designated by Reisner which had its own shaft.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: For the sake of eternal life and enjoying life after death.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Queen Meresankh III - the oldest case of bilateral Silent Sinus Syndrome (c. 2620/10 - 2570 BC)? Article in Anthropologie (Czech Republic) January 2018. Michael E Habicht, Patrick Eppenberger and Frank Ruhli

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://giza.fas.harvard.edu/ancientpeople/236/full/>

– Source 1 Description: Digital Giza. The Giza project at Harvard University. Meresankh III (G 7530-7540)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

– Source 1 URL: http://gizamedia.rc.fas.harvard.edu/images/MFA-images/Giza/Gizalimage/full/library/giza_mastabas/giza_mastabas_1/giza_mastabas_1.pdf

– Source 1 Description: THE MASTABA OF QUEEN MERESANKH III G 7530-7540 by Dows Dunham and William Kelly Simpson Based upon the excavations and recording of the late George Andrew Reisner and William Stevenson Smith Museum of Fine Arts - Harvard University Expedition

– Source 2 URL: http://www.gizapyramids.org/static/pdf%20library/bmfa_pdfs/bmfa25_1927_63to79.pdf

– Source 2 Description: THE MASTABA OF MERESANKH III (G7530/7540) IN THE EASTERN CEMETERY AT GIZA: AN ARCHAEOLOGICAL AND ART HISTORICAL ANALYSIS Laurel Flentye

– Source 3 URL: http://www.gizapyramids.org/static/pdf%20library/flentye_bem_3_2006.pdf

– Source 3 Description: BULLETIN OF THE MUSEUM OF FINE ARTS VOLUME XXV BOSTON, OCTOBER, 1927 NUMBER 151 TOMB OF QUEEN MERESANKH III MAIN CHAMBER, MAY 8, 1927

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general

populace)

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Archaeological mission/ Harvard-Boston expedition (April, 1927).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Years of excavation:

–Year range: 1927

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Name of excavation

–Official or descriptive name: Harvard- Boston Expedition, 1927.

Notes: Tomb excavated by George Andrew Reisner

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: This tomb is situated in an archaeological site among other ancient Egyptian monuments and tombs

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: This tomb is situated in an archaeological site among other ancient Egyptian monuments and tombs

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Specify

–Other [specify]: A burial place after a funeral procession, to help prepare for life after death

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

–Other [specify]: Burial place

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Queen Meresankh III – the oldest case of bilateral Silent Sinus Syndrome (c. 2620/10 - 2570 BC)? Article in *Anthropologie* (Czech Republic) January 2018. Michael E Habicht, Patrick Eppenberger and Frank Ruhli

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Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Archaeological mission/ Harvard-Boston expedition (April, 1927).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1927

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Harvard- Boston Expedition, 1927.

Notes: Tomb excavated by George Andrew Reisner

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Type of elevation

– Other [specify]: Giza Plateau

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: This tomb is situated in an archaeological site among other ancient Egyptian monuments and tombs

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: This tomb is situated in an archaeological site among other ancient Egyptian monuments and tombs

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: Burial place

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: A tomb

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: Mastaba above the ground, tomb below the ground

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: Mastaba above the ground and a tomb under the ground

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

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Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Giza plateau/ The Giza pyramids area

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

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Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: Reisner reconstructed the development of the Eastern Cemetery. Isolated structure designated by Reisner which had its own shaft.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: For the sake of eternal life and enjoying life after death.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: A burial place after a funeral procession, to help prepare for life after death

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Burial place

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: The offering chapel of the tomb of Meresankh III is unique in the unusual combination of features that it exhibits. Foremost is the emphasis on the role of the female members of the nobility of the Old

Kingdom, an emphasis which achieves its most notable expression in the reliefs of this chapel. Another feature to be singled out is the unusual and possibly unique placement of the tomb chapel beneath the large mastaba with which it is associated. A third notable feature is the extensive use of statuary cut in the tomb Walls. However, most notable of all is the interest of the scenes in relief, their extraordinary preservation and vivid colors, and the technical achievement and artistry of the sculptors and painters, the names of two of which have survived in the relief representations themselves. Texts and scenes, titles and names of the family represented the offering formulae, the list of estates, and the offering list.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Movable objects found during the excavation of the tomb

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction,

etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there gods depicted:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there humans depicted:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there animals depicted:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

— No

Notes: The decoration is viewable and people had regular access to the tomb.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there statues present:

— Yes

Notes: There were sixteen figures cut in the rock and four inserted in a niche in the south wall. In the row of ten female statues cut in the northern wall, there appear to be women depicted with either blonde or red hair, which would be the first example of this among the usually black-haired women depicted. The remaining figures are six statuettes of males, which are cut or inserted in the southern wall, and are mainly funerary priests. The inner room on the north has ten statues of women cut in a wide niche which takes nearly the whole length of the wall. The first figure on the right, and probably the first three, represent Hetep-heres II; the next four, Meresankh; and the last three, daughters of Meresankh. The ten rock-cut statues are part of the original decoration, as are also the four similar statues of women in the western wall of the room. The statuettes of the scribes: a scribe figure to the west is Khemten, the next Khemten-the-Younger, and the group of four, which are inserted, not cut in the living rock, are the children of Khemten-the-Younger, the heirs of the chief priesthood.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cult statues:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Statues of humans:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there paintings present:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions include the surviving decoration and inscriptions on Meresankh III's sarcophagus, which states that the sarcophagus was given to her by her mother, Hetepheres II. Inscriptions can also be found on the façade of the rock-cut tomb of Meresankh III (G7530sub), which give evidence for the date of the tomb. Niche inscriptions, possibly dating to Menkaura have also been found. If the entrance inscriptions refer to Menkaura's reign, Meresankh III could have been born earlier in Khufu's reign, ca. Year 7, or was younger at her death, ca. 40 to 45 years old, which the skeleton does not corroborate. Thus, the dates on the façade are probably a reference to the death and burial of Meresankh III during Shepseskaf's reign, which is important for establishing an overall date for the rock-cut tomb's decoration.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Texts and scenes, titles and names of the family represented, the offering formulae, the list of estates, and the offering list are all included.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The mastaba is associated with the Giza Plateau

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The tomb consists of two structures, the mastaba and the tomb itself, and they attached to each other

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: There is a unique placement of the tomb chapel beneath the large mastaba with which it is associated

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Humans

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The mastaba of Meresankh III (G7530/7540) is located in the 'en échelon' section of the Eastern Cemetery (G7000). This section consists of mastabas placed in a staggered arrangement. Reisner dated the initial part of the 'en échelon' section to the reign of Khafra, ca. 2520-2494 BC, following the conversion of the twelve original cores into eight twin-mastabas in the Eastern Cemetery. (G7000).

Reference: Flentye, Laurel. "THE MASTABA OF MERESANKH III (G7530/7540) IN THE EASTERN CEMETERY AT GIZA: AN ARCHAEOLOGICAL AND ART HISTORICAL ANALYSIS". *Bulletin of the Egyptian Museum* 3 (2006): 71-82.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The construction of mastaba G7530/7540 includes an earlier structure, G7520/7530, whose core construction and dimensions of 36.5 x 16.0 m. are similar to the twelve original cores in the Eastern Cemetery (G7000).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Earth

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Sand

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Clay

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Plaster

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Wood

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Grass

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Stone

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general

populace)

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The mastaba is associated with the Giza Plateau

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The tomb consists of two structures, the mastaba and the tomb itself, and they attached to each other

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: There is a unique placement of the tomb chapel beneath the large mastaba with which it is associated

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The mastaba of Meresankh III (G7530/7540) is located in the 'en échelon' section of the Eastern

Cemetery (G7000). This section consists of mastabas placed in a staggered arrangement. Reisner dated the initial part of the 'en échelon' section to the reign of Khafra, ca. 2520-2494 BC, following the conversion of the twelve original cores into eight twin-mastabas in the Eastern Cemetery. (G7000).

Reference: Flentye, Laurel. "THE MASTABA OF MERESANKH III (G7530/7540) IN THE EASTERN CEMETERY AT GIZA: AN ARCHAEOLOGICAL AND ART HISTORICAL ANALYSIS". *Bulletin of the Egyptian Museum* 3 (2006): 71-82.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The construction of mastaba G7530/7540 includes an earlier structure, G7520/7530, whose core construction and dimensions of 36.5 x 16.0 m. are similar to the twelve original

cores in the Eastern Cemetery (G7000).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Earth

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Sand

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Clay

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Plaster

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Wood

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Grass

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Stone

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people,

general populace)

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: The offering chapel of the tomb of Meresankh III is unique in the unusual combination of features that it exhibits. Foremost is the emphasis on the role of the female members of the nobility of the Old Kingdom, an emphasis which achieves its most notable expression in the reliefs of this chapel. Another feature to be singled out is the unusual and possibly unique placement of the tomb chapel beneath the large mastaba with which it is associated. A third notable feature is the extensive use of statuary cut in the tomb Walls. However, most notable of all is the interest of the scenes in relief, their extraordinary preservation and vivid colors, and the technical achievement and artistry of the sculptors and painters, the names of two of which have survived in the relief representations themselves. Texts and scenes, titles and names of the family represented the offering formulae, the list of estates, and the offering list.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Movable objects found during the excavation of the tomb

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: The decoration is viewable and people had regular access to the tomb.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Notes: There were sixteen figures cut in the rock and four inserted in a niche in the south wall. In the row of ten female statues cut in the northern wall, there appear to be women depicted with either blonde or red hair, which would be the first example of this among the usually black-haired women depicted. The remaining figures are six statuettes of males, which are cut or inserted in the southern wall, and are mainly funerary priests. The inner room on the north has ten statues of women cut in a wide niche which takes nearly the whole length of the wall. The first figure on the right, and probably the first three, represent Hetep-heres II; the next four, Meresankh; and the last three, daughters of Meresankh. The ten rock-cut statues are part of the original decoration, as are also the four similar statues of women in the western wall of the room. The statuettes of the scribes: a scribe figure to the west is Khemten, the next Khemten-the-Younger, and the group of four, which are inserted, not cut in the living rock, are the children of Khemten-the-Younger, the heirs of the chief priesthood.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Cult statues:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Statues of humans:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions include the surviving decoration and inscriptions on Meresankh III's sarcophagus, which states that the sarcophagus was given to her by her mother, Hetepheres II. Inscriptions can also be found on the façade of the rock-cut tomb of Meresankh III (G7530sub), which give evidence for the date of the tomb. Niche inscriptions, possibly dating to Menkaura have also been found. If the entrance inscriptions refer to Menkaura's reign, Meresankh III could have been born earlier in Khufu's reign, ca. Year 7, or was younger at her death, ca. 40 to 45 years old, which the skeleton does not corroborate. Thus, the dates on the façade are probably a reference to the death and burial of Meresankh III during Shepseskaf's reign, which is important for establishing an overall date for the rock-cut tomb's decoration.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Texts and scenes, titles and names of the family represented, the offering formulae, the list of estates, and the offering list are all included.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Humans

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Supernatural narratives

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Human narratives

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is divination present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The phrases, "honored before the great god", "the great god, lord of the desert", "the great god, lord of the necropolis", "the great god, lord of burial" have been mentioned in the tomb.

Reference: Dunham, Dows, and W. K. Simpson. The Mastaba of Queen Mersyankh the Third. Museum of Fine Arts, 1974.

https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Mastaba_of_Queen_Mersyankh_the_Third.html?hl=&id=XsrAAQAACAAJ.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are they sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– I don't know

Notes: But in the ancient Egyptian belief in general, yes, the role of the king is to represent the god.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are festivals present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: But I think grave goods would have been present originally.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: But given the greatness of the ancient Egyptians and their interest in funeral thought, it is logical that there were people responsible for the maintenance of the place, and perhaps they were the priests.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: But I think grave goods would have been present originally.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The phrases, "honored before the great god", "the great god, lord of the desert", "the great god, lord of the necropolis", "the great god, lord of burial" have been mentioned in the tomb.

Reference: Dunham, Dows, and W. K. Simpson. The Mastaba of Queen Mersyankh the Third. Museum of

Fine Arts, 1974.

https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Mastaba_of_Queen_Mersyankh_the_Third.html?hl=&id=XsrAAQAACAAJ.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– I don't know

Notes: But in the ancient Egyptian belief in general, yes, the role of the king is to represent the god.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: But given the greatness of the ancient Egyptians and their interest in funeral thought, it is logical that there were people responsible for the maintenance of the place, and perhaps they were the priests.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are festivals present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

— I don't know

Notes: But perhaps the priests were in charge of this place. At present, The Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities is in charge of this place.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– I don't know

Notes: Today, the Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities is in charge of this place

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– I don't know

Notes: But perhaps the priests were in charge of this place. At present, The Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities is in charge of this place.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– I don't know

Notes: Today, the Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities is in charge of this place

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Tomb of Meresankh III, Dunham, Dows, and W. K. Simpson. The Mastaba of Queen Mersyankh the Third. Museum of Fine Arts, 1974.

https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Mastaba_of_Queen_Mersyankh_the_Third.html?hl=&id=XsrAAQAACAAJ.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Dunham, Dows, and W. K. Simpson. The Mastaba of Queen Mersyankh the Third. Museum of Fine Arts, 1974.

https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Mastaba_of_Queen_Mersyankh_the_Third.html?hl=&id=XsrAAQAACAAJ.

Reference: Yes, Flentye, Laurel. "THE MASTABA OF MERESANKH III (G7530/7540) IN THE EASTERN CEMETERY AT GIZA: AN ARCHAEOLOGICAL AND ART HISTORICAL ANALYSIS". *Bulletin of the Egyptian Museum* 3 (2006): 71-82.